

SPHERE: A Dream About A Very Modern, Socially-Ubiquitous Virtual Reality World Social Internet Phenomena

A Metaverse & How I Had a Virtual Fight with a Friend Inside a Virtual Streetside Mini-Hotel over Virtual Food (APR 23, 2025)

In a dream, I've seen a time in the future when society globally goes rife with online, multiplayer virtual reality, user-reconfigurable virtual world games that are reminiscent of earlier such platforms as **Second Life**. The general trend across society was that more and more, people would meet

#dream #diary #jwl #futures #omens! #technology #forecasts #visions #business #ideas

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and interact with each other via these virtual worlds than say physically or via traditional text-and-pictures social media platforms. The likes of WhatsApp, Telegram, Tik Tok and such had become generally obsolete, and most online interactions were then happening via these virtual reality platforms. I happened to subscribe to and join one such platform, a very popular and widely utilised virtual world platform called SPHERE. I found that many people I knew had virtual presences and properties in that virtual world, including shops, restaurants, cars, wives and such! It was crazy. People in the real world would generally visit especially Internet Cafes, especially in our non-First World economies such as generally across Africa; they would access and use or interact in these virtual worlds via the high-speed internet and enhanced hire-to-play hardware found at Internet Cafes instead of using their own mobile computers such as smartphones or personal PCs (though, those with good personal hardware & the money to pay own internet bills generally played from anywhere via broadband Internet).

I noted that visiting these VR-gaming stations was as important or as popular as how people used to visit bars, sports-betting clubs or nightclubs! Also, such social centres were generally almost everywhere, and that many people including children and senior adults were readily found learning or participating in such virtual world platforms! People typically visited the VR-stations because of the subsidized Internet access costs, better hardware including more powerful processors in more modern computing consoles and especially for the sophisticated, though somewhat large to move-about-with VR body-mounting hardware; over-head visual displays, wearable computing gadgets, motion and gesture sensing equipment and such. It was such a big switch in Internet and Social culture that those who had lived in the early (now contemporary) era of social media via text chatting and posting status updates in text and photos would find the new era activities of creating updates directly in the virtual world far different, and arguably much easier, more natural!

One interesting memory I came across is that I went to eat at a restaurant one time, with my girlfriend who wasn't with me physically in the same place though. We sat at a table in this streetside restaurant, a local restaurant in downtown Kampala, and ordered for food including posho and some meat and vegetables. However, later on, when the food arrived, I noted that the waiter delivered a tray for my girlfriend and another

male customer seated at the same table with us instead of me. That other customer happens to have been my undergraduate OB, Steven/Stephen! There were also other people seated and waiting for their food at the same large table. However, after waiting for a while, I started to complain why the waiter had served another person instead of me yet me and my girlfriend had ordered for our food at the same time on the same order!

It so happens that during that confusion, Steven had told the waiter to also deliver the same food as we'd ordered for, and so when another waiter brought the food, they thought he was the one meant to receive that second tray! I got into a bitter argument over the food with Steven.. blaming him for having cunningly seized my food or having tricked the waiters to give him my food. Others joined in our argument, and before long, we got up and there was some slight fight before the restaurant staff arrived and moved me and my girlfriend to another less occupied table, as well as getting me my original food order. Twas crazy and so funny! Reactions from others, mostly our friends and neighbours kept coming in via the virtual world interactions and messages. Yet, in the actual world, we were all in totally different parts of the world, using the Internet at different times and from different places! Hahaha then I woke up.

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